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EFFECTS AS A MEANS TO SOCIO-EMOTIONAL BEHAVIORAL REACTIONS/RESPONSES IN PSYCHOSOCIAL COMPLEXES

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laboratively in the field of inclusive education and educational therapy. Both are in private practice and are actively promoting the specialty programs approved by IACT in Asia-Pacific region as they travel and lecture in different cities. Chia used to lead the IACT-Singapore Chapter until 2008 while Lim has started the IACT-Malacca Chapter in March 2017.

Definitions of effect and complex

You may have heard or read about Lucifer effect, Angel effect, Joseph effect ... and a long list of many other effects, often named after some biblical characters, but can also be named after some objects (e.g., fan effect), events (e.g., birthday number effect), experiences (e.g., false-fame effect), and other well-known personalities (e.g., Florence Nightingale effect) or people who discovered these effects (e.g., McGurk effect), too. One or more of these effects can lead to some kind of a psychosocial complex (e.g., Inferiority Complex). In this paper, I shall begin by exploring the different effects that cause us to behave socially and emotionally toward some positive or negative form of stimulus. I have defined the term *effect* as a state or condition of impression that inevitably follows an antecedent (as a cause or agent) and it is not an end in itself but a means to some kind of a socio-emotional behavioral reaction or response that may lead to some kind of a psychosocial complex.

Figure 1. Antecedents to effects to complexes

Understanding socio-emotional behavioral reactions and responses

As mentioned earlier, an effect is socio-emotional in nature and it is a means to some kind of a social-emotional behavioral reaction or response. It is important to take note that there is a subtle difference between reaction and response (see Mertz, 2017, for detail). When a person reacts, s/he is taking a defensive stance because s/he is at a disadvantage. Hence, in reaction, it is the emotion that takes the central role and this can lead to a downside, i.e., the loss of control. However, not every reaction is bad. There is also an upside and it is what we often call it “passion,” which

focuses on a purpose of why the person reacts in that manner.

Response is on the flipside of reaction and it is more thoughtful because it involves some rational thinking or reasoning. Although response may seem passive, its upside is an engaging opportunity that is considered positive and more civilized. A person responds by listening and acting forthrightly and from within. This is what I would call socio-emotional maturity consisting of two developmental strands: social maturity (Kegan, 1982) and emotional maturity (Erikson, 1959, 1968).

Briefly, according to Kegan (K) (1982), there are eight developmental phases of social maturity and they overlap nicely with Erikson’s (E) (1959, 1968) social-emotional (also known as psychosocial) development from infancy to adulthood: (1) Incorporative phase (K) (1-4 years of age), or Trust vs Mistrust (E) (birth-1 year of age) and Autonomy vs Shame and Doubt (2-3 years of age), which is the initial formation of self-concept different from others and the beginning of self-subjectivity development; (2) Impulsive phase (K) (4-6 years of age), or Initiative vs Guilt (E) (same age range), which concerns the impulses that drive self to take action to fulfill a need; (3) Imperial phase (K) (7-12 years of age), or (E) Industry vs Inferiority (same age range), is about an individual’s leveraging his/her interests vis-à-vis those of significant others who are being objectified, and there is an awareness of others through interaction with them as either agents or obstacles; (4) Interpersonal phase (K) (12-16 years of age), or Affiliation vs Abandonment (E) (early adolescence), concerns treating others as real persons with their own desires, needs, interests and so on, and empathy comes into play in this phase; (5) Institutional phase (K) (15-19 years of age), or Identity vs identity Confusion (E) (late adolescence) involves values and mores an individual can abstract and guide his/her life, and it is also during this phase that the individual realizes others have value systems different from his/hers; (6) Inter-individual phase (K) (20s-30s years of age), Intimacy vs Isolation (E) (same age range), concerns the appreciation of others’ different but equally valid value-systems, and the beginning to accept and understand true perspective of another person; (7) Self-transforming phase (K) (40s-50s years of age), or Generativity vs Stagnation (E) (same age range), is about an individual’s awareness of multiple value-systems appropriate for different events and beginning of his/her acceptance of contradictions in the value-systems; and (8) Integral perspective phase (K)

(60 and above years of age), or Integrity vs Despair (E) (same age range), has to do with integrity wherein an individual finds the value-system s/he uses is holistic in spite of contradictions, and able to resolve the apparent contradictions. As a baby matures into an adult, s/he develops progressively more objective and accurate appreciation of the social world he lives.

From effects to complexes

Briefly, a psychosocial complex has been defined as a core pattern of emotions, memories, perceptions, desires and wishes in one's unconscious mind organized around a common theme (e.g., power, wealth, status or sex) (see Shultz & Shultz, 2009, for detail). It is "a distorted thought and sensory pattern that has been deeply ingrained into an individual's psyche such that the individual's perception and decision-making process in terms of relating to others, emotional experiences and sense of self are altered" (Roy, 2015, para.1). There people who are inclined to developing certain psychosocial complexes by their very disposition. For instance, a person who has, in the past, always been scolded, criticized or talked down tends to develop an inferiority complex. In another instance, a narcissistic person has a higher chance of having a superiority complex.

Below are selected examples of socio-emotional effects and also selected examples of psychosocial complexes.

Selected examples of effects in alphabetical order

Angel effect. Described by Geiger (2013) as some kind of a neuro-experiential phenomenon encountered by people, especially when they are in danger, under severe distress or in desperate need, claiming that an unseen benevolent being referred to as "angel" has come to help them, providing them guidance, comfort and advice. Neurologists have called this effect sensed presence phenomenon and attempted to explain how it happens, believing that it is a neurological product of the brain under tremendous stress. This effect could be a remnant of the bicameral mentality, which Jaynes (1976) argues the human mind was once a state in which its cognitive functions were divided between the "speaking" part of the brain and the "listening and obeying" part of the brain – the bicameral mind. The concept of bicameral mentality or mind will not be covered here as it is beyond the scope of this paper; its issue remains controversial even today.

Dunning-Kruger effect. This is a cognitive bias observed in an individual with low ability suffering from illusory superiority but whose ability has mistakenly been assessed to be much higher than it really is. Dunning and Kruger (1999) have attributed it to a metacognitive incapacity, on the individual's part of his/her low ability, to recognize his/her ineptitude and evaluate his/her competence accurately. Often, children with attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder, autism spectrum disorder, and deficits in attention, motor control and perception display such an ineptitude.

Job effect. In the Bible, Job is depicted as a righteous and prosperous man, who, unfortunately, was beset with horrendous disasters taking away everything that he held dear. He struggled to understand the circumstances surrounding him and thus began his search for answers to the challenges he was experiencing. This effect is probably the toughest to bear, especially when one has to anguish over his/her plight without losing hope or cursing with language of profanity or blaming others for the misfortunes, but accepting that everything happens for a reason and as according

to God's will. It involves a firm belief that suffering produces perseverance, which in turn produces character, and character, hope (see Romans 5:4 for the exact verse).

Joseph effect. A biblical character whose envious brothers sold him away as a slave and he was brought to Egypt where he was bought by Potiphar, a Pharaoh's officer. Joseph often made his decision to uphold his integrity instead of doing what could have benefited him at the time. As a result of his moral integrity, Joseph was alleged by Potiphar's wife of taking advantage of her and found himself in jail. Although imprisoned, Joseph continued to diligently applied himself to whatever tasks he was entrusted and received "favor in the sight of the keeper of the prison" (Genesis 39: 21). According to Marshall (2013), "[T]hrough Joseph's work ethic and conduct were likely a factor in this (situation), we must remember that God was with Joseph and blessed him (Genesis 39:21)" (para.8). Despite having no hope or possibility of promotion, Joseph carried on to give his best in whatever circumstance he found himself. In the end, God's favor caused Joseph's work ethic and effort to be noticed and rewarded. This is what has been termed as the Joseph effect in action!

Google effect. According to Washington's Top News Press (2015) report, most Americans suffered what is now known as Google effect (also known as digital amnesia). It is the tendency to forget information found readily online by using Internet search engines such as Google or Yahoo. According to Krieger (2011), people who display Google effect are less likely to remember certain details they believe will be accessible online, but their ability to learn information offline remains unchanged.

Lucifer effect. Zimbardo (2007) describes the point in time when a normal person first crosses the boundary between good and evil to engage in an evil action. Lucifer effect represents a transformation of the individual's character that is significant in its consequences. One best example of Lucifer effect is the well-known episode known as the Stanford Prison Experiment. A group of college student volunteers participated in this landmark experimental study where they were randomly selected to play guards and inmates and placed in a mock prison context. Within a week, the study had to be halted when the researchers found that these ordinary college students were transformed into either brutal, sadistic guards or emotionally disturbed prisoners.

Selected examples of psychosocial complexes in alphabetical order

Cinderella complex. This is found mainly among females, who are afraid of being independent, and tend to be over-dependent on their male counterparts (such as male colleague, boyfriend or husband). Very often these females choose to carry on or stay in dysfunctional relationships in order to feel cared, albeit by a very abusive and manipulative partner (Roy, 2015, para.4). This is a subtype of dependency complex seen in females.

Hero complex. A person with this complex is very prone in his/her attempt to gain recognition. Very often, such a person will tackle very tough situations that he/she has self-created in order to get a sense of self-worth. It is quite common for those who are not doing well in their profession and desire to feel good about themselves. However, most actions are simply a desperate need to compensate for their past failures.

Jonah complex. Jonah is a biblical prophet who was sent by God to prophesy the destruction of Nineveh but he attempted to escape the divine responsibility. This complex has been described as the fear of success, especially from one's own greatness, and evading from one's destiny or avoiding the opportunity to exercise one's talents. As a result, it prevents an individual with this complex from attaining self-actualization or realization of one's potential.

Martyr complex. Among the many different complexes, this is one of those few very serious complexes that requires immediate attention and early treatment. This complex can escalate to the point of self-injury in both physical and emotional terms. An individual with martyr complex strongly believes that his/her "life is all about suffering and ... actually want to have more of this suffering in order to receive a form of sympathy from others" (Roy, 2015, para.8). S/He often attempts to influence others about the "tortures" s/he is going through and even exhibits his/her terrible state of injuries. It can escalate into psychosis over time and psychiatric and/or psychoanalytic treatment is urgent.

Peter Pan complex. Found mainly among males, this is often associated with a young adult man who behaves like a quintessential "boy who refuses to grow up." In such a complex, the male individual is often seen as immature or childish and he tends "to avoid responsibilities with excessive laziness, with no clear direction in life or career development and chronic procrastination of problems" (Roy, 2015, para.4). It is a subtype of dependency complex seen in males.

What can we do to help such clients?

From this short article, the theoretical understanding of socio-emotional effects and their reactions and/or responses as well as the psychosocial complexes can provide counselors and therapists a simple guideline involving the following steps 1 and 2 what to do in identifying effects and complexes before they decide on the appropriate strategy to be used in the treatment plan:

Step 1: Identify the socio-emotional effect:

- 1.1 Know the antecedent that has resulted in some kind of a socio-emotional reaction or response; and
- 1.2 Note down the reactions/responses to identify the suspected effect.

Step 2: Identify the psychosocial complex:

- 2.1 Interview the client to find out about his/her pattern of emotions, memories, perceptions, desires and wishes; and
- 2.2 Organize all the information given by the client around a common theme to identify the suspected complex.

Step 3: Decide on a follow-up plan of action with an appropriate strategy (e.g., cognitive behavioral therapy, solution-focused therapy, reality or choice therapy).

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